

“A Perceptual Study on Mobile Banking”

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Jisha James &
Aishwarya, A.
“A Perceptual Study
on Mobile Banking.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 6, no. S1, 2018,
pp. 1–5.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2532911](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2532911)

Jisha James

*Student (II M.Com Accounts), PG Department of Commerce & Management
Mount Carmel College (Autonomous), Bengaluru*

A.Aishwarya

*Student (II M.Com HR) PG Department of Commerce & Management
Mount Carmel College (Autonomous), Bengaluru*

Abstract

“Financial Institutions must be able to deliver an easy to navigate, a seamless digital platform that goes far beyond miniaturized online banking offering.”- Jim Marous.

Mobile Banking is one of the areas mobile commerce have extension with other mobile commerce. It's associated with the customers associated in various fields. We aim to determine customer perception on mobile banking. Customers have various opinions on mobile banking provided by various service providers.

This study concentrates benefits and awareness on mobile banking in general. To achieve this purpose, questionnaire was used as an instrument to gather primary data from the respondents using Random Sampling Technique. Total number of responses collected were 107 responses. The paper concludes by providing suggestions and measures on Mobile Banking.

Keywords: Mobile banking, Awareness, Perception.

Introduction

Mobile Banking is a service provided by a bank or other financial institution that allows its customers to conduct financial transactions remotely using a mobile device such as a smartphone or tablet. Unlike the related internet banking it uses software, usually called an app, provided by the financial institution for the purpose. Mobile Banking is usually available on a 24 hour basis. Some financial institutions have restrictions on which accounts may be accessed through mobile banking, as well as a limit in the amount that can be transacted.

Transactions through mobile banking may include obtaining account balances and lists of latest transactions, electronic bill payments, and funds transfers between a customer's or another's accounts.

It reduces the cost of handling transactions by reducing the need for customer to visit a branch for non-cash withdrawal and deposit transactions. Mobile banking does not handle transactions involving cash, and a customer needs to visit an ATM or bank branch for cash withdrawal or deposits.¹

Literature Review

Sadi and Noordin (2011)²: This study deals with the customer attitude was correlated negatively with cost. Their intention to use mobile banking services decreases with increase cost, therefore customer must be aware of the cost saving feature of mobile banking services through awareness.

Singh Srivastava, and Srivastav (2010)³: This study deals with the cost incurred by the customers have a negative impact on their intention to do mobile banking transactions. Mobile banking device is considered to be cost effective option for customers to manage transactions, get account information and payments.

Sharma and Singh (2009)⁴: This study deals with the reason for less usage of mobile banking in India may arise because of security issues like frauds, misuse of accounts and user friendly app. But these challenges in using Mobile payments may decrease what time and by increasing knowledge of mobile banking.

Research Gap

Many studies have been conducted on Mobile Banking. From the above literature review it is evident that few research has been conducted on mobile banking based on its less usage, cost incurred by customers and cost saving. Hence, the present study is taken on general people's opinion on mobile banking.

Statement of the Problem

Before the study was undertaken most the people's views were same. But once the study is undertaken we got to know that there is different opinion from different people.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to know the perception in general towards the Mobile Banking. Keeping this in view, the following secondary objectives has been set up:

- To know the awareness about Mobile Banking services.
- To know the benefits on Mobile Banking.
- To know the preferences of Mobile banking services.

Scope of the Study

The study was undertaken to assess the perception in general towards Mobile Banking, it's awareness, benefits and also preferences. For this purpose, respondents from Bengaluru city are selected.

Limitations of the Study

The "Perceptual Study on Mobile Banking" has few limitations:

- The study is exclusively based on primary data with a limited sample size.
- The study has been restricted to Bengaluru city in general.

Research Methodology

The primary data is collected through an online survey. The survey is carried out by means of self-administered, structured questionnaire and secondary data is collected from articles, research papers of various journals.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Chart: 1

INFERENCE: From the above graph 1 it is observed that out of the total 107 respondents, 72 people agree as to mobile banking is secure, 15 people disagree and 20 people are neutral.

Chart: 2

INFERENCE: From the above graph 2, it is inferred that out of 107 respondents awareness about mobile services through mass media is 52, through agent it's 5, through bank directly it's 30, through SMS from mobile operator it's 2 and from friends or family it's 18.

Chart: 3

INFERENCE: From the above graph 3, it is inferred that out of 107 respondents preference of mobile banking services through telephone call is 4, through TV advertisements it's 41, through email it's 12, through SMS it's 29 and through word of mouth it's 21. It can be observed that preference of mobile banking services through TV advertisements is more when compared to others.

Chart: 4

INFERENCE: From the above graph 4, it is inferred that out of 107 respondents benefits of mobile banking on cost saving is 12, on time saving is 39, on 24hour access is 52 and physical security is 4. It can be observed that benefits of mobile banking on 24hours access are more when compared to others.

Findings

Following are the findings on mobile banking

- From the above study, 72 people agree that it is secure using mobile banking.
- From the above study, awareness about mobile banking services through mass media is more when compared to others.
- From the above study, 41 people get to know through TV advertisements for preference of mobile banking services.
- 52 people say that 24 hours access is the most preferred benefits of mobile banking services.

Conclusion

Mobile Banking is an emerging service has not been widely adopted pointed out the need to find out the various consumer adoption factors. The study identified the benefits, awareness, preference on mobile banking services. I would suggest that preference of mobile banking services through SMS and word of mouth should increase.

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